

Lived Experiences of Teachers in Far Flung Teaching Community in West Malungon District, Sarangani Division

Romel A. Zamora

Department of Education/West Malungon District/Datal Baca Elementary School
Barangay Datal Batong, Malungon, Sarangani Province
Region XII, Philippines

Abstract:- The objective of this study is to determine experiences of teachers in the far flung teaching community in West Malungon District, Sarangani Division, Region XII, Philippines. This research employed a qualitative method based on focus group discussions and individual interviews of teachers in their lived experiences in far flung community. Based on the findings, teachers' experiences vary in assessment process, classroom management, contextualization, learning activities, and decision making process. They also mobilized the community through their school best practices, community linkages, and behavioral approach. Furthermore, the stakeholders support mechanism in far flung schools is being shown by providing educational support towards teaching of teachers, teachers' professional development, learners' performance, and stakeholders' other initiatives. These experiences made teachers realize that stakeholders' involvement in all school's programs, projects and activities play a vital role to have a positive impact on the lives of learners and community.

Keywords:- Lived Experiences, Far-Flung School, Assessment Process, Classroom Management, Contextualization, Learning Activities, Decision Making.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teachers are the custodians of any top-down teaching innovation or education reform (Anderson et Helms, 2001). In order to facilitate policy driven changes in teaching content and practices, it is helpful to understand how these innovations spread to teachers and how this process can be catalyzed.

The remote schools in the Philippines still face a shortage of teaching resources and educators are constantly challenged to provide quality basic education in the sector. The conditions of the remote school require passionate people, teachers committed to providing the quality services to the public. Also, Philippine education nowadays faces perennial problems in various learning contexts, such as; shortage of textbooks, facilities and classrooms, particularly in the public school system of qualified teachers to be aware of (Sun. Star Pampanga, 2017).

Basically, teachers are responsible for teaching basic knowledge to students. At the same time, education is considered such because of the extreme dedication to meet expectations or in addition to all costs. Also, teachers play an extraordinary role in children's lives during the formative years of their development and the importance of teachers is something that cannot be underestimated. They are involved in shaping learners into responsible citizens of the country.

Republic ACT 10618, Sec. 2, states that it is a state policy to protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and to take appropriate measures to make that education accessible to all. The state will establish, maintain and support a comprehensive, adequate and integrated education system relevant to the needs of people and society, encourage non-formal, informal and indigenous learning systems, as well as self-learning, independence and extracurricular studies, in particular those that meet the needs of the community.

II. RESEARCH DESIGN

➤ **Objectives:**

This study aimed to determine experiences of teachers in the far flung teaching community. Specifically, the researcher sought answers to the following sub-problems:

- What was the profile of teachers in the far flung teaching community?
- What were the experiences encountered by teachers in the far flung teaching community?
- How did teachers mobilize the community to participate in educational activities?
- How did stakeholders provide support mechanisms in dealing with educational challenges?

III. METHODOLOGY

This study used qualitative research design. Qualitative research is an effort to understand the nature of an environment and the experiences that others have in this context (Merriam, 1998, quoted by Zeek, 2002). Qualitative research does not predict what will happen in the future; rather, it is an analysis that provides information to those interested in the events of a particular environment and time. The main informants of the study were seven (7) public elementary school teachers, two (2) school principals, for a total of nine (9), who are assigned to remote schools in West Malungon district who have for at least one (1) year or more years of teaching experience.

The researcher identified the participants based on their history; they were teachers in a very remote teaching community; they served as informants for this study. Their

personal experiences of the various challenges they faced within the classrooms were critical to the study's findings, conclusions and recommendations.

The researcher used key informant interviews and focus group discussion to gather the needed data for the study. The researcher collected data by drafting a list of guided questions which he asked the informants. The researcher kept in mind the areas and specific topics to be covered during the interview while going deep into the details.

Focus group discussion was also utilized in data gathering of this study. Focus group discussion was guided by the researcher through pre- determined open-ended 29 questions. Each participant was encouraged to talk about the topics or questions asked by the researcher.

In gathering the data, the researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Sarangani to conduct the study in West Malungon District, Municipality of Malungon specifically in three (3) public schools in far flung area, namely: Datal Bila Integrated School, Datal Baca Elementary School, and Nicomedes Sunio Elementary School.

When approval was granted, the researcher sent an official communication to the school heads of the 3 public schools to arrange suitable dates for data collection. Participants were interviewed at their respective schools and the duration of each interview is approximately 45 minutes.

All interview sessions are tape recorded, and during the interview, the researcher also took down notes.

Thematic analysis was used to examine, classify, tabulate, and test the collected data. Gibson and Brown (2009) defined thematic analysis as examining common elements, differences and relationships in the data collected. Most of the expected data have been assigned codes. After classifying the data and comparing the contrasts, the subjects that responded to the research problems were identified.

The goal of the thematic analysis was to identify themes, that is, patterns in important or interesting data and use these themes to address problems. R Analytical Tool R is an open source statistical software that was also utilized.

IV. FINDINGS

➤ *Teachers' Profile:*

Teachers in far flung schools of West Malungon District, Division of Sarangani use their own motorcycle to reach their school stations. The data reveals that one of the informants has to travel 50 kilometers and above from school to residence, while eight of them have to travel for about less than 50 kilometers. But, as to the distance of the schools from the Sarangani division it is approximately 95 km.

As to the distribution of informants by their grade level of teaching. There were four (4) of them teaching kindergarten to grade five learners, and two (2) teachers teaching grade six learners. While the three (3) among the respondents of the study are school heads who actively supervise the implementation of curriculum. Moreover, among the informants, one of them has a teaching position of head teacher 1, and eight of them occupy the teacher-1 position.

The results also revealed that most of the respondents finished bachelor of elementary education major in general education. The qualification to teach in elementary and pre primary schools is a bachelor's degree in elementary education. To teach secondary education, the teacher must have either a bachelor's degree in education with a major and a minor; an equivalent degree but also with a major and a minor; or a bachelor's degree in arts and/or sciences with at least 18 education units for teaching in high school. Therefore, teachers in elementary grades are discouraged to teach in secondary level.

The results also revealed that far flung schools in West Malungon District are stations that are placed in an area with inconvenience of travel due to dangerous terrain, isolation and extreme weather conditions. In this case, based on the results of the study, teachers in the said location are qualified to avail the special hardship allowance as stated in Department of Education Memorandum No. 038, s. 2018 or the provision and computation of the special hardship allowance for fiscal year 2018. Moreover, National Budget Circular No. 514, guidelines on the grant of special hardship

allowance, states that the allowance shall be granted to qualified teachers under any of the following situations: being assigned to a hardship post; performing multi-grade teaching; carrying out mobile teaching functions; or performing functions of non-formal education (now Alternative Learning System) coordinators. The qualified teachers may either be resident or transient having regular or temporary appointments.

➤ *The Experiences Encountered by Teacher in Far Flung Teaching Community:*

From the discussion of the focus group it is revealed that different experiences of teachers in far flung schools in the district of West Malungon, Sarangani division vary in assessment process, classroom management, contextualization, learning activities, and decision making process.

• *Assessment Process:*

In the assessment process, teachers in the far flung teaching community consider the learners' needs to learn, learner's capabilities, types of tests to be administered, and learners' skills towards accomplishing tasks. By providing a series of assessments, teachers are able to quickly remedied where the learners are disadvantaged. They also mentioned that having a variety of tests is an effective way to gauge how widely learners learn about the lessons. However, it is also important to carefully assess whether the testing tools used in any test ensures accuracy to avoid confusions among learners of the school. The school heads or school administrators are significant individuals that can assist classroom teachers to sustain quality delivery of curriculum. Commitment and dedication towards work are also the keys to touch the lives of learners in the community.

These are their stories:

- ✓ *"Sa akon dapat ang pagtudlo may dedikasyon ka gid dapat, sa pagtudlo kada adlaw naging bahagi ka sa kinabuhi sang bata, ang lesson wala lang basta basta ginatudlo kundi pwede sa kuhaan sang maayo nga lesson nga pwede magamit sang mga kabataan sa ila nga pagpanginabuh every day". (For me, the teachers should have dedication. In our daily teaching experience, we become part of the lives of children, and the lessons are being taught to have learnings that can be used in the daily living of children).*

In addition, participant 5 said: "Ang sa akon naman, ang pagtudlo kinahanglan may ara gid sang puso, kapoy man ang obra ta as teachers sang mga bata, pero kung makita ta nga ang mga bata may ara gid nga na learn para sa aton, kanami gid ina sa feeling. so dapat, may dedikasyon gid sa pagtudlo". (In my case, teaching should be coming from the heart, it is hard to teach children, but it feels good when we see them that they are learning coming from us. Teaching should have dedication).

• *Classroom Management:*

In classroom management techniques among the teachers in far flung schools, it is good to note that they fostered positive discipline among learners they are

teaching. They protect the rights of every learner towards basic and quality education by adhering to the mission and vision of the Department of Education. Teachers also use positive communication techniques to elicit positive responses and actions from learners. Accordingly, it has the ability to turn negative feelings and thoughts into positive and helps learners create a positive impression.

Additionally, teachers in far flung schools listen attentively to every learner's voice. They believe that each learner is a unique individual which each of them has something to accomplish that would help them improve their learning and skills.

Moreover, by building good relationships among learners in far flung schools is an important predictor of academic commitment and achievement. Indeed, it is the most powerful weapon of teachers, when they seek to foster a favorable learning climate, and positive relationships with their learners. Learners who perceive their teachers as more caring have better performance results (Boynton & Boynton, 2005).

✓ Participants 7 said that: *“It is very important na sa aga pa lang ma set na sa good mood ang mga bata, and it’s nice to see na ang mga bata malipayon nga naga learn sang bag o na mga lessons”*. (It is very important to poster good vibes in the morning for the kids to be inspired to learn new things).

- *Contextualization:*

To meet the needs of learners in far flung schools and to understand the content of their lessons, teachers utilized the available materials that can be seen or found in their locality. This is to make it easier for learners to connect with the subject that they are learning. It is also an effective way to reach the competencies that learners are achieving.

Basically, the purpose of contextualization is to make teaching effective using available materials in the community. The study also revealed that contextualization is an effective way for learners in far flung schools to easily understand the lessons taught by teachers. This will also make it easier for teachers to achieve their goals, and to prevent learners from being confused in their studies, and most importantly, teachers must have instructional learning materials that are appropriate to children's interests, abilities, and needs.

According to Snyder (2002) contextual basic skills education involves teaching academic skills in a specific context to which those skills should be applied, such as philosophy. With this, far flung school teachers believe that using contextualized learning materials will give learners an opportunity to learn, and to understand the concepts of their lessons. However, it is also important for teachers to ensure that all learners will have a good learning experience in class.

✓ *Participant 3: “sa paghimo nako sa akong lesson plans, gina consider usa nako ang mga instructional materials nga pwede ra makita sa palibot, kay diri sa bukid walay mga available materials nga pwede mapalit sa tindahan. Sa paghatag ug instructions gina consider pud nako ang abilities sa bata sap ag absorb sa akong mga instruction arun akong ma meet ang akong objectives sa kana nga adlaw”*. (In making my lesson plans, I see to it that there are available materials that can be found in our surroundings, stores for school supplies in the community are not available. Also, in giving an instruction to the learners I see to it that it is based in the abilities of the kids to meet my objectives for the day).

✓ *Participant 9: “Ako pud, gina consider jud nako ang learning styles sa mga bata, in fact naga conduct jud kog klase klase nga approach sa pag cater sa needs sa usa ka bata arun walay mabilin sa ilaha sap ag proceed nako sa next nga lesson”*. (Me too, I also consider learners’ ability to absorb the lessons as they have different learning styles, in fact, I used different teaching strategies to cater the needs of the learners and for them to be ready in the next lessons to be discussed).

- *Learning Activities:*

Learners’ participation is a measure that reflects the quantity and quality of learners’ participation in their courses and in any other aspect of their educational program. It also echoes a learner's interaction and cooperation with his classmates and teachers. In other words, learners’ involvement is the measure of a potentially successful learning experience for all concerned.

Teachers in far flung schools use group work activity to develop teamwork among learners to acquire knowledge and carry out activities through collaboration Interaction.

✓ *Participant 5: “Sa akong lessons, involve jud tanang estudyante sa akong mga activities na ginahimo arun ma motivate sila nga mag learn sa new lesson nga akong ginatudlo. Nagaconduct kog mga activities na group work. Akong ginapa utilize sa ilaha ang mga availbale materials nga anaa lang sa ilang palibot or community”*. (In my lessons, I involved all the learners in different learning activities for them to become motivated to learn. I group work activities by utilizing the available materials in the community).

- *Decision Making Process:*

In far flung schools, teachers hold meetings led by the school heads in order to make some right decisions to address any concerns and priorities of their schools. Different stakeholders of the schools such as; Municipal Government Unit, Barangay Local Government Unit, School Governing Council, Parent-Teacher Association, and other private individuals are involved in the decision making processes. In the crafting of School Improvement Plan, Annual Implementation plan and some adjustment plans stakeholders are also involved in the process to exercise their duties and obligations to achieve the goals of the schools for their learners in the community.

It was also revealed in the study that community's opinions and suggestions are being respected to resolve problems and issues that may affect the learning outcome of learners.

✓ *Participant 1: "Syempre, sa mga experiences nga there are times nga ara sang mga desisyon nga indi magkaisa tapos ang mga...ano gani tawag sina? Nga mag-abot ang bottom line gid nga kailangan pag-abot sa decision making bisan magkaiba-iba man kamo sang mga opinion o mga suggestions at the end of the day kay amo man tong kailangan para sa mga bata indi gud sang iba-iba so indi ta madula sa aton nga tracking indi ta in line sa ginatawag bala nga related sa mission vision sang eskwelahan nga iba-iba pud ang padulngan sang idea sang mga teachers."* (Of course, there are times that the teachers have different decisions, opinions or suggestions, but, at the end of the day we only have one decision to make that everyone should have to agree for us to keep on track in the mission and vision of the Department).

The result of the study implies that teachers in the far flung teaching community in West Malungon District, Sarangani Division, Region XII, Philippines have common experiences in facilitating learning to learners in remote areas. Through this study, the researcher was able to understand how the system works to the lives of people in the community, how it reproduces existing inequalities and values that support it, and teachers are the key support people responsible for facilitating the teaching-learning process and educational activities of learners (Congress of the Philippines, 2001).

➤ *How Teachers Mobilize Community to Participate in Educational Activities:*

From the discussion of the focus group, it can be deduced that teachers in far flung schools mobilize the community to participate in educational activities through their best practices, community linkages, behavioral approach and teachers' professional development.

• *School Best Practices:*

The unity among teachers, community and stakeholders has been one of the best practices of the schools in remote communities as they believe that everyone has an important role to play in attaining the Department of Education's mission and vision and to solve problems that occur in school.

Study also revealed that Community Resource Map is also utilized to mobilize the community to participate in educational activities. Community resource mapping is sometimes referred to as resource mapping or environmental scanning.

By involving the community in all programs, projects and activities of the school, community members were able to accomplish their tasks effectively and efficiently.

Additionally, each elementary and secondary school are tasked to organize a Parent Teacher Association (PTA) to provide a forum for the exchange of ideas, the discussion of problems and the formulation of solutions related to the school program. This association offers a place to effectively achieve full parental cooperation for effective implementation of the program (Teresita Sibayan, 2017). Teachers in far flung schools stated that the very idea of a general assembly organized by the PTA in each school is very important because it acts as an open road and discussion platform for teachers and parents. The goal of this assembly is a meeting of minds and hearts to elevate the school environment and improve the categorical conditions that children or learners are experiencing.

Schools in far flung areas used to make action plans in accomplishing a particular task. It is an organizational strategy for identifying the necessary steps towards a goal. Consider the details, it can help limit the configuration of an organization and is efficient because it saves resources rather than trial and error. A written action plan also acts as a signal for an organization's responsibility. Moreover, teachers at far flung schools are used to involve people in the community in formulating action plans.

✓ *Participant 4: "Para maka create kami sang linkages sa community and para maempower man ang kada myembro sang community, kami sa school nagahimo kami sang amon nga action plan kung sa diin ang mga persons involved ara lang sa community. Gituyo siya namon nga himuon para ila pud ma exercise ila kalabutan sang eskwelhan and to empower them that they can make a difference".* (For us to create community linkages and to empower every member of the community, the school made an action plan that involves persons within the community. It has been meant to be done to exercise their rights as part of the school and to empower them that they can make a difference).

In addition, participants 5 added:

✓ *Participant 5: "Sa eskwelhan para magkaroon sang klase-klase nga stakeholders dapat may ara gid sang plano nga pagahimuon. Over the years diri sa amon nga eskwelhan, klase klase na nga mga indibidwals ang nagbisita sa amon para lang magbulig, and ina siya amon gid ginapasalamat sang dako kay naging possible ang mga ginapangandoy namon sa eskwelhan".* (For the school to have different stakeholders there should be a plan to be made. Over the years, the school has different individuals who visited the school and to extend help, and that's what we are thankful for because we're able to realize our desires for our school).

➤ *Community Linkages:*

Teachers in far flung schools practice different ways of reaching parents and other stakeholders. One of these is by sending an invitation or a letter informing them about the school's activities and programs.

- *Parents' Involvement:*

According to García and Thornton (2014) current research shows that the family commitment to learning helps improve learner achievement, reduce absenteeism and restoration of parental trust in the education of their children. Learners with parents or healthcare professionals involved in learner education, obtain higher marks in tests, have better social skills and show better behavior. Which something that community and the world in general need as it strongly contributes to reducing crime and poverty. Ideally, it would be helpful to have a higher one percentage of participation of parents in the education of their children.

It was also revealed in the study that Constant Communication among teachers, learners and other stakeholders is very significant as it is a dynamic process that needs the mind and courage to face other individuals and transmit the message effectively.

- ✓ *Participant 1: "To maintain constant communication with our community para mag participate sila sa mga educational activities sang school is ginainvolve namon sila sa planning, implementation, and evaluation. We make them feel na part sila sa tanan nga activities sang school, we communicate with them also through school letters, announcements, and social media. (To maintain the constant communication with our community and for them to participate in educational activities in school, we involve them in planning, implementation, and evaluation. We make them feel that they are part of all school activities, we communicate with them also through school letters, announcements, and social media).*
- ✓ *Participant 5: "Sa pag maintain sang constant communication with the community amon sila ginasali sa mga meetings sang school and even sa mga outreach programs nga ginahimo sang mga iban pa na stakeholders, para ma feel nila nga they are belong and importante sila sa eskwelahan regardless sa ila nga economic status". (To maintain constant communication with the community, we involve them in school meetings and even outreach programs of other stakeholders to make them feel that they belong and that they are important regardless of their economic status).*

- *Teachers' Behavioral Approach:*

Teachers in far flung schools strive to develop good relationships among parents in the community in order to safeguard the rights of learners in learning. They believe that teaching can be effective when working with parents at school.

The teachers in far flung schools build trust in the people of the community because they believe that by giving an opportunity to people to work independently can make them feel that they belong to the group. Trusting them is important to make every member of the school more motivated to work.

Respect is also of great importance in everyday life of teachers in far flung schools. Children are being taught by

them to respect parents, teachers and seniors. For them, this must be possessed by every individual in school to foster good relationships and collaboration.

- ✓ *Participant 2: "Tama nga approach and respeto sa ila nga pagtuo kag prinsipyo makabulig gid siya sap ag maintain sang maayo nga komunikasyon kag relasyon. Regardless sang tagsa-tagsa ka prinsipyo kag pagtuo dapat ma fell nila nga sila ginapamatian kag ginatahod". (Right approach and respect to their principles can help to the good communication and relationship. Regardless of different principles and beliefs they they must be felt that they are being heard and respected).*

- *How Stakeholders Provide Mechanism in Dealing with Educational Challenges:*

From the discussion the following themes and sub-themes emerged from individual interviews and focus groups. These are; stakeholders' support towards teaching, stakeholders' support towards teachers' professional development, and stakeholders' support towards learners' performance, stakeholders' other initiatives.

- *Stakeholders Support Towards Teaching:*

- ✓ *Contextualization of Learning Materials:*

Based on the results of the study, parents and other stakeholders in far flung schools are involved in contextualizing instructional learning materials to effectively address the learning difficulties of learners. The concept of contextualization, localization and indigenization of the curriculum is based on the idea that learners learn best when familiarity in the classroom has meanings in their life. The things that learners do and are connected are learning that lasts forever. As far as the rule of learning through doing is concerned, practical learning and manipulative learning are also mandatory to perform localization and contextualization in teaching. In addition, Mazzeo (2008) broadened the definition, describing contextualized teaching and learning as a "diverse family of teaching strategies designed to more transparently connect the learning of fundamental skills and academic or professional content by concentrating l 'teaching and learning directly in concrete applications in a specific application for the context that is of interest to the learners.

- *Stakeholders' Support Towards Teachers' Professional Development:*

- *Monitoring:*

Despite the distance of the schools from the district, teachers are regularly monitored by DepEd officials or school administrators in order to direct them in their way of teaching. Also, they are provided with significant interventions to address the concerns inside the classroom.

- ✓ *Participant 9: "Ang mga stakeholders sang school naging partner namon sa pagbabasa sa mga bata nga dili kaayo makabasa, nagatabang sila sa pagmonitor sa reading performance sang mga bata". (The stakeholders of the school became our partners in making the non-*

readers to become readers, they're helping us also to monitor the reading performance of the learners). Mentoring. Mentoring can be an effective way to enhance the teaching skills of teachers as it gives an opportunity to teachers to explore new things and new experiences.

- *Inspiration:*

Teachers in far flung schools are inspired by the school administrators and district supervisor to perform their tasks effectively despite of the challenges they encountered in teaching. Inspiration is the process of being mentally stimulated to do or feel something, especially to do something creative.

Participant 5: "Through SLAC sessions na gina offer sa among school, damo ko natun an isip 21st century teacher. I am more inspired to do more with my chosen profession". (Through SLAC sessions offered by the school, I have learned a lot as 21st century teachers. I am more inspired to do more with my chosen profession).

- *Stakeholders' Support Towards Learners' Performance:*

- *Educational Learning Materials:*

The support of stakeholders to learners in far flung schools play a vital role in attaining the targets of the schools. Teaching instructional materials can refer to a number of teacher resources, and these were provided by the division, and other partners of the schools.

- *Financial Support:*

Financial education is increasingly important, and not just for investors. It is becoming essential for the average family trying to decide how to balance its budget, buy a home, fund the children's education and ensure an income when the parents retire. On other hands, the schools in these remote areas are lucky enough to have stakeholders who actively participate in schools' programs, projects and activities by giving financial support to schools.

✓ Participant 6: "*The stakeholders of the school nagapaningkamot gid hatag sa ila suporta sa financial nga panginahanglanon sa school, basta maghatag lang kami letter nga naga ask sa ila assistance sa procurement sa gamit sang eskwelahan*". (The stakeholders of the school are doing their best to give financial support for the needs of the school, provided, that the school will give letters asking assistance for the procurement of school materials).

- *Stakeholders' Other Initiatives:*

- *Health Service:*

Due to difficulties in remote areas, it is difficult for parents to bring their children to medical facilities for their health, but it's good to hear that there are few NGOs who come to schools to meet the health needs of young children. It's just like the story of teachers in far flung schools:

✓ Participant 6: "*Ako naman, kung may ara ko problema sa klase most especially sa mga bata, ang mga ginikanan or kinsa pa na stakeholders nga pwede palapitan naga*

effort gid para maaddress ang akong concerns, for example sa health sa mga bata nagahatag sila mismo sang mga bulong and may foundation pud gaadto diri para maghimo sang dental check up". (In my case, if I have problems in my class, most especially with the learners, the parents or any stakeholders that can provide help really do their efforts to address my concerns, for example with the health of the learners, it is them who make initiatives to provide the medicines, and there is foundation also who came here to do the dental check-up for the learners).

- *Monthly Brigada Eskwela:*

Brigada Eskwela is a nationwide initiative by the Department of Education (DepEd) that mobilizes thousands of parents, alumni, civic groups, local businesses, non-government organizations, teachers, learners, and individuals who volunteer their time and skills to do repairs, maintenance work, and clean-up of public elementary and secondary schools. Meanwhile, the stakeholders of the schools in the far flung area of West Malungon District, Sarangani Division have an initiative to secure the learning environment of learners, and it's what they call a "monthly brigada eskwela". Stakeholders believe that this endeavor will provide a conducive learning environment for learners and to make them safe from any harm that may occur in the surrounding.

- *Reading Program:*

Schools in far flung areas have some issues in reading, such as; poor reading comprehension skills, issues with decoding, improper directional tracking, and the like. Some stakeholders of schools in highlands provide reading intervention in order to address the difficulties in reading.

As participant said:

✓ Participant 1: "*Ang among mga stakeholders naga support sa among pagtudlo pinaagi sa paghatag ug mga instructional materials. Naging partners pud namo sila sa pag implement namo sa reading program sa school. They are also present during homeroom meetings ang culmination days. Concerned pud sila sa mga bata kung paano mag improve sa ilang pag eskwela*". (The stakeholders extended their support in our teaching through the giving of instructional materials. They became our partners also in conducting the school reading program. They are also present during homeroom meeting and culmination days. They are also concerned about the learners' improvements with their studies).

Based on the findings of the study, the result implies that stakeholders are working together for the sustainability of the learners' basic needs in education. According to Levy (2002) sustainability is staff to maintain the convictions and basic values of a program (culture) and to use them to guide the adaptations of the program over time, maintaining better and better results. Moreover, the teachers in far flung schools are continually faced with insufficient educational materials and other resources. However, with these

challenges that they have they become more resilient and inspired to perform their tasks effectively.

V. CONCLUSION

Remote schools are difficult to reach and often dangerous. Traveling to and from the nearest accessible road requires stamina and courage. It is a practice in the Philippines to assign novice teachers to less attractive places, such as remote schools. In some cases, the desire of new teachers to find work for financial reasons is often the main reason why new teachers carry out teaching activities in remote places. In addition, teachers bring their theoretical frameworks to the classroom. They bring their theories and practices with a routine personal history and level of change ability (Hubbard et al., 2006).

Generally, the informant teachers have different experiences in the far flung teaching community. Their experiences vary in assessment process, classroom management, contextualization, learning activities, and decision making process.

Moreover, teachers in far flung schools in West Malungon District, Sarangani Division, Region XII, Philippines mobilize the community through their school best practices, community linkages, and behavioral approach. In terms of how the stakeholders provide support mechanism in dealing with educational needs, they performed it through extending supports towards teaching of teachers, teachers' professional development, learners' performance, and stakeholders' other initiatives.

This implies that cooperation and unity among individuals in the community are the keys in attaining the Department of Education's vision and mission. Emily R. Lai (2011) cited that collaboration is the mutual commitment of the participants in a coordinated effort to solve a problem together. She added that collaborative interactions are characterized by shared objectives, symmetry of the structure and a high degree of negotiation, interactivity and interdependence.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Avellis, G., Agrimi, A., Grasso, G., Di Ciano, M., & Surico, F. (2014). Education and Training projects of Apulian ICT LivingLab. *ADVANCES in EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES*, 63.
- [2]. Baltusite, R., & Katane, I. (2014). The structural model of the pedagogy students' readiness for professional activities in the educational environment. In *Paper dipresentasikan di International Scientific Conference: REEP*.
- [3]. Brusa, A. P. (2020). The Difficulty of Teaching Historical Landscape: Observations Starting from the Italian Situation. In *Handbook of Research on Citizenship and Heritage Education* (pp. 377-406). IGI Global.
- [4]. Buțiu, C. A. (2014). Roma social inclusion through higher education. *Journal of Linguistic and Intercultural Education*, 7, 55-68.
- [5]. Calverley, J. R. (2020). *Adolescents' Perceptions of Walking versus Cycling to School in Rural Otago, New Zealand* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Otago).
- [6]. Carr-Fanning, K., & Mc Guckin, C. (2018). The powerless or the empowered? Stakeholders' experiences of diagnosis and treatment for attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder in Ireland. *Irish journal of psychological medicine*, 35(3), 203-212.
- [7]. Deng, W. J., Hoekstra, J. S., & Elsinga, M. G. (2020). The urban-rural discrepancy of generational housing pathways: A new source of intergenerational inequality in urban China?. *Habitat International*, 98, 102102.
- [8]. Diaconeasa, M. C., & Chirculescu, R. E. (2016, November). The level of employability in the Romanian rural area. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Competitiveness of Agro-food and Environmental Economy Proceedings, Bucharest, Romania* (pp. 10-11).
- [9]. Dimitropoulos, Y., Holden, A., Gwynne, K., Do, L., Byun, R., & Sohn, W. (2020). Outcomes of a co-designed, community-led oral health promotion program for Aboriginal children in rural and remote communities in New South Wales, Australia. *Community Dental Health*, 37, 1-6.
- [10]. Drew, M. B., Potter, J., & Stover, C. (2020). Complicated Lives: A Look into the Experiences of Individuals Living with HIV, Legal Impediments, and Other Social Determinants of Health. *Quinnipiac Health LJ*, 23, 81.
- [11]. Fedeli, V., Lenzi, C., Briata, P., & Pedrazzini, L. (2019). *EU Regional and Urban Policy: Innovations and Experiences from the 2014–2020 Programming Period*. Springer Nature.
- [12]. Fernandes, M. E., Lopes, A. S., & Sargento, A. L. (2019). Improving stakeholder engagement in local strategic planning—experience sharing based on Portuguese examples. *Policy Studies*, 1-16.
- [13]. Furness, M., & Vollmer, F. (2013). *EU joint programming: lessons from South Sudan for EU aid coordination* (No. 18/2013). Briefing Paper.
- [14]. Goldstein, T., Koecher, A., Baer, P., & Hicks, B. L. (2018). Transitioning in elementary school: parent advocacy and teacher allyship. *Teaching Education*, 29(2), 165-177.
- [15]. Hong, X., Liu, P., Ma, Q., & Luo, X. (2015). The way to early childhood education equity-policies to tackle the urban-rural disparities in China. *International Journal of Child Care and Education Policy*, 9(1), 5.
- [16]. Hudečková, H., & Husák, J. (2015). Rural school in the context of community-led local development. *Scientia agriculturae bohemica*, 46(1), 33-40.

- [17]. Jack, H., Wagner, R. G., Petersen, I., Thom, R., Newton, C. R., Stein, A., ... & Hofman, K. J. (2014). Closing the mental health treatment gap in South Africa: a review of costs and cost-effectiveness. *Global health action*, 7(1), 23431.
- [18]. Katona-Kovacs, J., & Bóta-Horváth, N. (2014). *Corporate Innovation a Missing Success Factor of Rural Development—Lessons Learned from the Past Decade* (No. 712-2016-48517).
- [19]. Kereszty, O. Language Teachers' Professional Learning. *Beliefs and Behaviours in Education and Culture: Cultural Determinants and Education*, 54.
- [20]. Koutsouris, A., & Zarokosta, E. (2020). Supporting bottom-up innovative initiatives throughout the spiral of innovations: Lessons from rural Greece. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 73, 176-185.
- [21]. Kronberga, G., Bite, D., & Kruzmetra, Z. (2017, September). CREATIVE LEARNING METHODS IN PRACTICE: EXPERIENCE OF LATVIAN EDUCATORS. In *Economic Science for Rural Development Conference Proceedings* (No. 46).
- [22]. Lash, M., & Raimbekova, L. (2020). A modern-day early childhood teacher education initiative on Tajikistan's historic silk road: Dushanbe to the roof of the world. *Journal of Early Childhood Teacher Education*, 1-17.